
The Jain remnants in Bangladesh: the possibility of the discovery of a long Jain past and its legacy in the East Bengal

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[Abstract]

From the successive excavations in the Northwestern region of Bangladesh a significant number of the Jain artifacts and the ruins of the Jain temples have been discovered. The Bengal's glorious past cannot be comprehended without recognizing its rich Jain heritage. But in many cases Jain vestiges of Bangladesh are intermingled with the Buddhist artifacts. The discovered artifacts remind us that we are not serious enough in our archeological studies and investigations, otherwise we might have found many more Jain artifacts and the remnants of the Jain temples. Some proper and meticulous investigations may unveil a forgotten and lost Jain era of the East Bengal. The incumbent essay wants to delve into the Jain artifacts and temples and reconsider the possibility of the discovery of a rich Jain legacy in the East Bengal of the undivided India (i.e. the present Bangladesh), if we continue our scientific researches and archeological investigations.

Introduction

Tīrthāṅkara Mahāvīra (c. 599 BCE - c. 527 BCE/425 BCE) was a contemporary of *Gautam Buddha* (c. 563/420 BCE-c. 483 BCE/400 BCE), the founder of Buddhist faith and the Magadha was their abode and the breeding ground of the both Jainism and Buddhism. Both fall within the ambit of the *Śramanic movement*. The West Bengal and the present Bangladesh are not far away from their abode because the ancient Magadha is now geographically located in Bihar of Uttar Pradesh (UP), India. A considerable number of Artifacts and the relics of Jain temples have been found in the West Bengal. Even the place *Bardhaman* a city and municipality in the state of West Bengal, is ascribed to *Vardhamāna*,

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a name of the 24th Tīrthāṅkara i.e. Mahāvīra. It means that in the ancient Bengal Jainism flourished and burgeoned excessively. Mahāvīra spent some times in *Astikagrama*, according to the Jain scripture of *Kalpa Sūtra*. This place was situated in the present-day's West Bengal.

The possibility of a lost Jain civilization yet to be discovered, which had proliferated in the ancient East Bengal

The present Bangladesh was a part of the undivided Bengal, which is called the East Bengal even today. Therefore, it is highly possible that the Jain ideology was propagated here excessively and in order to practice Jainism a lot of Jain temples (*Jinalaya* or *Jain Mandirs*) and monasteries were built here for the Jain teachers and preachers, theology students and the Jain pilgrims (*Vihāra*). Even a Jain settlement might have been here, we cannot abort this speculation. Still today we can trace out the vestiges of the Jain legacy, when we dig out a lot of Jain artifacts and the ruins of the Jain temples in both the East and the West Bengals. The remnants that the archeologists have excavated from underneath and have been excavating off and on, support our speculations. Anupam Jash has written on the Bengal brand of Jainism evincing that even the vestiges of Jain civilization in Bengal are present in *Kalpa Sūtra*. Hence the greater Bengal includes also the present Bangladesh:

“According to *Kalpa Sutra*, Godasa, a disciple of Bhadrabahu, founded a school named after himself as *Godasa-gana*. In course of time it had four branches which were known as Tamraliptiya, Kotivarsiya, *Pundravardhaniya* and *Kharvatika* named after three very well-known places in ancient Bengal, currently known as, Tamluk (*Tamralipta* in western Bengal), Dinajpur (*Kotivarsiya* in north bengal), Rajshahi (*Pundravardhaniya*, now in north Bangladesh) and Champa (*Kharvatika* in south-western part of ancient Bengal) respectively. It appears from such evidence that Jainism had deep roots in Bengal, especially in northern, western and southern part of Bengal.” (Jash: 2017: 99)

Anupam Jash has also cited from *Epigraphica Indica* and insinuated the existence of a Jain civilization in the East Bengal i.e. largely in today's Bangladesh (*Epigraphica.Indica.*, XX, pp. 59ff.):

“A definite piece of evidence of the presence of Jainism in Bengal is furnished by a copper-plate, dated year 159 of the Gupta era (around 479 A.D.) found in Paharpur in North Bengal, now in the Rajshahi district, Bangladesh, famous for the big Buddhist *Stūpa* and monastery of the Pala period. The copper-plate records the gift of land by a Brahmin couple, for the construction of a temple and worship of the divine *Arhat* image at the *Vihara* of Vata

Gohala which was presided over by the disciples of the *Nirghantha Sramanacarya* (Jaina preceptor) Guhanandin, belonging to the *Pancastupa* section (*Nikāya*) of Kasi (Varanasi). This record proves the existence of Jainism in Bengal during the Gupta period. This shows that even those who were not professed Jains, including the Brahmins, had great reverence for the Jaina *Arhats* and were quite liberal in outlook and accommodative in regard to the adherence of other religions. ” (Jash: 2017: 102)

The areas of Bangladesh, where Jain artifacts and remnants of the Jain temples have been discovered

a) Mahasthangarh

Mahastangarh is located in Bogura in the Rajshahi division of Bangladesh. This place is historically very important as the remnants of a huge Buddhist monastery have been discovered here. As the Buddhist and Jain faiths were born and developed contemporarily, the archaeologists were almost sure that they might discover something of the Jain traditions. In 1879 Alexander Cunningham found some Jain idols and he handed over those to Varendra Research Museum of Rajshahi.

b) Dinajpur

In Dinajpur the ruins of a Jain temple is still visible. The idols have been preserved in the Dinajpur Museum.

c) Damdampir of Jessore

A 7 inch statuette of *Tīrthāṅkara Mallinātha* has been excavated and the archeologists opined that this sandstone statuette dates back to some 1800 years. The statuette was dedicated to *Tīrthāṅkara Mallinātha*. On the statuette “*Bhagavān Mallinātha*” (Lord Mallinātha) – this writing is engraved. The archeological department of Khulna discovered the statuette during an excavation period.

d) Paharpur of Naogaon

In Paharpur a copper-inscription was discovered, which insinuates the existence of Jain Vihāra in the Botgohali village. In 1980-81 CE during an excavation period a big structure was discovered. The archeologists assume that this dating back to over 18th century and was a part of a Jain Vihāra.

e) Bogura and Meherpur

There are two Jain temples still existing in Bogura and Meherpur. One temple has been remaining in Satmatha of Bogura and another in Bakshi Lane of Meherpur. In the early 19th century some Jain merchants and traders of Gujarat built these temples.

f) Lalmai of Comilla

Some engraved stone and mud idols, complete and incomplete, were found in the hilly area of Lalmai; the area is located in the western part of Comilla.

The Jain artifacts in the Bangladeshi museums

Some significant Jain artifacts and remnants of the Jain temples have been excavated and the artifacts have been preserved in the Dhaka, Khulna, Dinajpur and Rajshai's Varendra Research museums. The Dhaka museum is the national museum of the country. The excavation started here from the British colonial era. So, we better delineate the history sometimes. Here we are mentioning some of the most significant artifacts:

- a) A bluish statuette of Lord Mahāvīra in Khaḍgāsana Mudra, height 73.6 cm, is now preserved in the National Museum of Bangladesh, Dhaka. The statuette was made within 10-11 century AD.
- b) A bluish statuette of Lord Pārśvanātha in Khaḍgāsana Mudra, height 60.9 cm, is now preserved in Dinajpur Museum. The statuette was made within 10-11 century AD.
- c) A bluish statuette of a Tīrthaṅkara in Khaḍgāsana Mudra, height 93.9 cm, is now preserved in Dinajpur Museum. The statuette was made within 9-10 century AD.

- d) A bluish statuette of Lord Śhāntinātha in Khaḍḍgāsana Mudra, height 65 cm, is now preserved in Varendra Research Museum of Rajshahi.
- e) A bluish statuette of Lord Ṛṣabhadeva in Padmāsana Mudra, height 99 cm, is now preserved in Varendra Research Museum of Rajshahi.
- f) A sandstone statuette of Lord Mallinātha, height 7 inch, preserved now in the Khulna museum.

In most of the cases the discovered Tīrthānkara statuettes of Bangladesh are similar to those found in the West Bengal like the engraved figures of the Tīrthānkaras. The Tīrthānkaras are standing in most of the cases as Shubha Majumder has presented in his work. (Majumder: 1998: 11-16) It also reminds us that once the East Bengal was unified with the West Bengal.

Jain legacy in the East Bengal of the undivided India

In the East Bengal the Jain civilization thrived through centuries and from the rubbles, artifacts and the remnants we can surmise the long historicity of Jainism in this land. In 1927 A copper plate dates back to 159 Gupta Era (479 AD) was discovered in the Pāhārapura Baud'dha Vihāra (i.e. Paharpur Buddhist monastery). It was found in the northeast corner of the monastery. The plate mentions that it was a donation of a Brahmin couple to Jain Acharya Guhanandi of *Nikāya* at Vata Gohli, identifiable as the neighboring village of Goalapara. (Asher: 1080: 15) Sukumar Dutt also mentioned this. (1988: 371) This Vihāra is also called *Somapura Mahavihāra*.

The architectural remains of the vast Somapura Mahavihāra cover 11 hectares (27 acres) of land. *Sheo Sing* wrote (1982) that this Vihāra was an important intellectual centre (and we surmise a melting pot as well - author) for Dharmic Traditions such as Buddhists , Jains and Hindus alike. Masud et al (2007: 53 (8): 1639–1650) have mentioned that the area of the complex is 8.5-hectare (21acre), where 177 cells, Viharās, numerous stūpas, temples and a number of other ancillary buildings were built. The outside walls with ornamental terracotta plaques are still manifesting the influence of these three religions.

Hence, the question arises, did a *mélange* of the three religions rise in Bengal during the Pāla dynasty? The syncretic Buddhism from the Mahāyāna tradition emerged during the Pāla Empire (750-1161 CE). *Banglapedia*, one of the most reliable sources on history and archeology of Bangladesh, vividly mentions that:

“The representations of divinities of hierarchical religion are few and far between. The Brahmanical as well as the Buddhist gods are equally illustrated in the plaques. They are the principal varieties of Shiva and other Brahmanical gods like Brahma, Visnu, Ganesha and Surya. Buddhist deities, mostly of the Mahayana School, including Bodhisattva Padmapani, Manjushri and Tara are noticed here and there. Well-known stories from the Panchatantra are represented with evident humour and picturesque expressiveness.” (Banglapedia; See: [Paharpur - Banglapedia](#))

Banglapedia mentioned the Jain legacy within this ambit of Mahāyāna tradition:

“*Inscriptions* discovery of an inscribed copperplates and some stone inscriptions has helped us to determine the chronology of the different periods. The copperplates found in the northeast corner of the monastery is dated in 159 Gupta Era (479 AD). It records the purchase and grant by a Brahman couple of a piece of land for the maintenance of the worship of Arhats and a resting place at the Vihara, presided over by the Jaina teacher Guhanandin. This Vihara, which was situated at Vatagohali in the 5th century AD, must have been an establishment of local celebrity.” (Ibid)

Banglapedia also mentions some material reasons of the Mahāyāna tradition’s abreast position of the Jainism.

“It is worth mentioning here that the same name Vatagohali is found on a mutilated copperplate found at Baigram dated 128 GE (448 AD). The mention of the name Vatagohali in a record from Barigram, which is about 30 km to the north of Paharpur, indicates that the two places Vaigrama and Vatagohali may not be far away from each other. The Guhanandi Vihara at Vatagohali must have shared the fate of other Jaina establishments in Pundravardhana, when anarchy reigned supreme in Bengal in the late 7th century or early 8th century AD. At last peace was established and the Pala

Empire was securely founded in Bengal in the 8th century AD and Dharmapala at Somapura established a magnificent temple along with a gigantic monastery. (Ibid)

Then Banglapedia continues with the assessment of *K.N. Dikshit*. It says,

Dikshit believes that the monks in the new Buddhist Vihara might have been given the royal permission to appropriate the land belonging to the Jaina Vihara and kept the original charter in their possession. According to him 'this supposition can alone, explain the find of the plate among the ruins of the Buddhist Vihara'." (Ibid)

In Somapura Mahavihāra many terracotta plaques are still representing Hāra (Śiva) and *Pārvaṭī* above the meditating Buddha. It seems that the plaques represent them to be *the power house* of Buddha. *Pārvaṭī* is the *sambhavi shakti* of Shiva; so they are also together here. It is also an insignia of the influence of Shaktism on the Bengal brand of Buddhism. However, one can watch the terracotta representation of Balarāma, the elder brother of *Lord Kṛṣṇa*, *Vināyaka* (Gaṇeśa), *the Nāgas* and many stories of the *Purāṇas* like the water churning of the gods and demons in a body to help *goddess Śrī* to resurface and so forth. Some elegant panels are still unscathed, which depict the most popular themes of *Mahābhārata* and *Rāmāyana* and various other incidents from daily life of the rural folk. The small chambers of the monks and pupils indicate us to the esoteric practices of the *Tantrik Buddhists* especially the adherents of the *Vajrayāna*. Atisa Dipankara (982 CE–1054 CE) went to Tibet during this Pāla reign. The Paharpur iconographies contain the vestiges of Tibetan Buddhism and hence one will realize that the Tibetan Buddhism was influenced by Hinduism invariably. Therefore, we may call the *Somapura Buddhism* to be a ‘*penumbra*’ of Hinduism, because here one can distinguish Buddhism from Hinduism but cannot dissociate.

Anupam Jash has cited from *The Divyavadana*, a Buddhist text, records a tradition which shows that the *Nirgrantha* or Jaina religion was established in Pundra or north Bengal at the time of Samrat Asoka. Jash has written, “It is said that the lay followers (*upasaka*) of Jainism in the city of *pundravardhana* (north Bengal) had painted a picture representing Buddha falling at the feet of *nirghantha*, and on hearing this Asoka massacred 18000 *Ajivikas* of *pundravardhana* on a single day.” Jash has also mentioned in brackets that he gleaned information from *Divyavadana* (p.427). He has also mentioned that the account gets mixed up with the *Nirghanthas* and *Ajivikas*, but the name of the sect is uniformly given as

Nirghanthas in the Chinese translation. (Jean Przyluski, *La Legende de l'Empereur Aśoka*, p.278).

We can remind that Pundra's a mentionable part is now in the *Rajshahi* and *Rangpur* divisions of today's Bangladesh.

Conclusion

The artifacts and ruins of the Jain temples imply that the Bengal witnessed a long Buddhist era but with the admixture of the Jain traits. Because of the open ended circumference of the Mahāyāna school, a syncretic Buddhism emerged during the Pāla Empire. Due to the contemporariness of the Jainism and Buddhism, some common traits of Jainism helped Buddhism to embrace it. But at the same time the Jain civilization burgeoned under the syncretic mode of a special denomination of the Mahāyāna school, which did not hamper the Jain socio-culture rather extended its hand benevolently in order to ensure the survival of the Jain culture in Bengal. Therefore, in the East Bengal the Jain civilization rampantly burgeoned and survived especially during the Pāla Empire. Thus, a mélange civilization of three major religions i.e. Hinduism, Buddhism and Jainism developed in this certain part of Bengal like Bengal's other parts.

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Paharpur - Banglapedia